

Mismatch between Qualification and Employment in the Democratic Republic of Congo

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Abstract

Instruction and education are recognized as important and determining factors in entering the job market. However, more and more graduates are finding it difficult to get a job and find themselves forced to accept a downgraded job, that is, one that requires a lower qualification than that conferred by their diplomas. Thus, based on the case of the Democratic Republic of Congo, this study set itself the objective of measuring the extent of this phenomenon and highlighting the underlying factors. Using data 1-2-3 from surveys carried out in 2012 and 2018 covering the entire extent of the DRC on employment-related aspects and living conditions of households, this study discusses the measurement of downgrading through its three approaches taken from the literature (normative approach, subjective approach, and subjective approach) and finally presents the theoretical model and the empirical model of the factors explaining the determinants of downgrading when hiring

Keyword: Hiring, competence, downgrading, education

INTRODUCTION

The diploma logically constitutes a major asset on the job market and, for the employer, a pledge of the knowledge acquired and a productive potential easily employable by the company [Boudabbous, Ali Mâalej, 2011]. Since the end of the Second World War, the quantitative development of schooling as a central objective of development policies was almost unanimous. The main reason is that, on the one hand, education is one of the main instruments to facilitate social mobility and to remunerate individual skills and, on the other hand, a more educated workforce can increase economic growth and support the overall efficiency of the economic system [Dolton and Vignoles, 2000].

For example, the work of [Nauze-Fichet and Tomasini 2002] underlines in the context of France that a higher education graduate has a three times lower probability of being unemployed than an unqualified individual, 3 years after his exit into the education system.

For a given person, having a high diploma protects against unemployment and provides skilled employment. However, in situations of distortion of the labor market or crisis, new generations entering the labor market with increasingly higher qualifications find it more difficult to find jobs corresponding to their level of qualification [Giret et al, 2006; Nauze-Fichet and Tomasini 2002]. Indeed, in the context of mass unemployment, young graduates may be led to accept low-skilled jobs, possibly by renouncing the vocational guidance for which they were intended. It is this discrepancy between the level of diploma required to exercise a job and the level of the diploma of employees in this job that we qualify as downgrading [Nauze-Fichet 2002].

One of the forerunners of research on downgrading in hiring finds in particular that the profit rate for a level of diploma significantly decreased in the United States around the 1970, and attributes this fall to an excess of supply of graduates. [Freeman, 1976]. The value of its results is that it challenges the belief that a university degree was a profitable investment and a virtual guarantee of economic success. While [Espoir 2016] tends to see dysfunctions from the supply of graduates, other work such as that of Forgeot and [Gauttief 1997] and [Nauze-Fichet and Tomasini 2005] in France, point to the responsibility of companies through the demand for labor. Their many questions concern the influence of age, gender, social and ethnic origins, the role of economic conditions, and technical progress.

In the Democratic Republic of Congo where there is a shortage of qualified jobs, where the structure of diplomas does not evolve at the same rate as that of jobs, we have always considered that studies were security and a springboard on the social ladder.

According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO 2008], the 2000s in the DRC were marked by the strong educational policy. The diversification of the training offer, in higher education, in particular, contributed to the increase in the number of graduates, to the raising of diploma levels, which caused a competition effect between the most graduates.

In the face of rising education levels, the growth of skilled jobs has not been sufficient to secure employment for the most highly educated generations. According to the African Development Bank [ADB 2012], out of 9,000 young people who leave Congolese universities each year, less than 100 find a job. The most highly qualified gain access to employment, but they are often forced to accept positions that are not commensurate with their level of training. Unemployment has also contributed to the downgrading phenomenon. According to the Central Bank, the unemployment rate, which was 59% in 2010, rose to 65% in 2014 [BCC Report, 2014]. Faced with rising unemployment among young people, they have chosen to protect themselves by extending the duration of their studies, thereby increasing the risk of downgrading. The present study draws heavily on previous studies and seeks to answer the question of the extent of the downgrading to hiring in the DRC.

The objective of this study is therefore to assess the level of downgrading on hiring in the DRC as well as the factors underlying it.

LITERATURE PAPER

Doazan 2014, using the Céreq "Generation 92" survey, studied the downgrading of young people who left the education system in France in 1992. By testing the relevance of the statistical and subjective measures of downgrading, they find that 56.1% of young graduates of STS and IUT are downgraded if we use the statistical measure of downgrading while only 48.4% consider themselves downgraded. However, taken as a whole, the two downgrading measures used are opposed to more than 37% of young people. While 22.6% are statistically downgraded, they consider themselves not downgraded, and conversely 14.8% say they are downgraded when they are not downgraded according to the statistical criterion. These authors note that five years after their exit, young graduates are less downgraded than when they first worked.

Guironnet 2005 also uses the céreq surveys, on graduates from higher education between 1984 and 1996, to analyze the evolution of the determinants and the incidence of over education. By favoring endogenous modeling of over education in determining wages, and taking into account the selection bias induced by unemployed graduates finds that the phenomenon of over education is far marginal and the proportion of employees downgraded doubles in 12 years. The link between diploma and access to employment was reinforced for those leaving higher education, but paradoxically the probabilities of access to high positions in the professional hierarchy deteriorated considerably between 1987 and 1999. All of the diplomas are devalued and at the same time, the distribution of employment has greatly deteriorated.

Voirol and Hanhart, 2015 compared the normative method and the subjective method using data from the Netherlands on young Dutch people, one year after leaving school: they show that the correlation of the number of years of study required for the job held is 0.66 at the individual level and 0.78 at the aggregated level for each profession. For the subjective method, the average level of education required was 13.2 years and 23% of young people had a job whose required training was lower than their level of education. For the normative method, the average level of education required was 11.4 years and 65% of young people were considered to be over-qualified. For these authors, this phenomenon is more structural than cyclical; it is inflated by the approach of individuals in search of the highest diploma, thereby aggravating and amplifying the imbalances between the supply and demand for diplomas.

Forgeot and Gautié 1997 study the professional integration of young people and the downgrading process in France. Using a diploma/profession correspondence table, these authors find that the proportion of over-graduates increased sharply between 1985 and 1995. The results of their study indicate that women are more affected by downgrading than men: in 1995, more than 24% of young women were over-educated, compared to less than 18% of young men. Beginners are logical, on average, more overqualified. Downgrading decreases with seniority on the labor market, regardless of the level of training. Downgrading also varies by industry.

Using aggregated data from 25 studies concerning different countries and different periods, [Groot and Maassen van den Brink 2000] presents a three-step analysis of the job quality of the generation of higher education graduates who entered the market in 2004 work. These authors find that the feeling of over-education is particularly strong for young people who occupy jobs of poor quality: half of them feel they are used below their skill level. This assessment is in line with the assessment that they have of the level of diploma necessary to occupy this job: almost half of them believe that a higher diploma is not necessary. On the salary dimension, a third of young graduates consider themselves poorly or very poorly paid, regardless of the quality of the jobs they hold.

Boudabbous and Ali Mâalej 2011 conducts a study that focuses on access to a first job for a cohort of young people leaving higher education in Tunisia. The survey was carried out among students who obtained their diplomas at the end of the 2004/2005 academic year, with masters and specialized masters graduates, but also short cycle diplomas (3 years). It turned out that 64.88% of the individuals retained are in a situation of over-education. Also, using a probit model, they find that waiting times, gender, social background and qualifications are the factors that explain over-education.

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

The data

The data used in this study comes from the 1-2-3 survey. This survey which covers the whole extent of DR Congo was carried out by the National Institute of Statistics of DR Congo in collaboration with DIAL and AFRISTAT in 2004-2005, and subsequently replicated in 2012 but not on the same people. On the basis of these two surveys, the 1-2-3 database for 2005 and 2012 were produced respectively. Indeed, the 1-2-3 survey comprises three phases: the first phase of this survey covers employment, unemployment, and household activity conditions (phase 1: employment survey). The second phase consists of carrying out a specific survey of the heads of informal units on their working conditions, their economic performance, their mode of integration into the productive fabric, and their prospects (phase 2: a survey on the informal sector). The third phase is a survey of household consumption. It consists of estimating the standard of living of households, measuring the respective weight of the formal and informal sectors in their consumption, and analyzing the determinants of the choice of different places of purchase (phase 3: a survey of household consumption). The use of the two bases is motivated by the need to record the behavior of the variables over time.

Choice of the measure of downgrading on hiring

Within the framework of this research, the statistical approach is privileged following the nature of the data in our possession. Above all, it is necessary to specify the procedure that will be followed to measure the extent of the decommissioning.

For this purpose, a contingency table crossing the different types of diplomas or titles sanctioning training in the national education system (Diploma/title) on the one hand and the different socio-professional categories, on the other hand, is used. Table 1 below is constructed. The boxes in the table correspond to the observed numbers n_{lC} associated jointly with the modality Y_l of the variable Y online ($Y \in \{y_1, \dots, y_l, \dots, y_L\}$), and the modality x_c of the variable X in column $X \in \{x_1, \dots, x_c, \dots, x_C\}$.

The totals in the table, in row n_l and in column n_c , show the marginal numbers. They correspond to counting according to a flat sorting of the variable row in column.

In the box corresponding to the function between the total in row and in column, the overall size ($n = n$) of the generic form of a contingency table is as follows:

Table 1: Generic form of the contingency table

Y*X	x1	...	Xc	...	xC	Total
y1	nl1	...	n1c	...	n1C	n1
...						
Yl	nl1	...	Nlc	...	n1C	Nl
Yl	nL1	...	nLc	...	nLC	nL
Total	n.1	...	n.c	...	n.C	n=n

In this table, **n1c** represents the observed numbers of the couple **(xc, y1)**. By analyzing this generic form of the contingency table and adopting the approach used by Forgeot and Gautie (1997), we can measure the extent of downgrading on hiring. Under the assumption of independence between X and Y, the theoretical number of the couple **(xc, y1)** is given by

For each box **(l, c)**, we can then consider as a first approximation that the diploma-profession situation is:

- “normal” if **n1c >** (frequent agreement between modalities X and Y),
- “atypical” if **n1c <** (rare agreement between modalities X and Y).

In the second case, it is determined whether the "atypical" situation corresponds to an "over classification", that is to say, the case of an individual who is undereducated about the qualification requirement of his profession or downgrading, that is, the case of an over-educated individual. Concretely, in the case of the DRC, the association between the level of education (diploma) and socio-professional category can appear as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Adaptation of the table used by Forgeot and Gautie 1997, in the context of the DRC

Diploma	Diploma socio-professional category					
	Senior executive	Collaboration framework	Agent-control	Employee, skilled worker	Employee, semi-skilled worker	Maneuver
Doctorate, 3rd cycle	Normal	Overeducated	Overeducated	Overeducated	Overeducated	Overeducated
Bachelor	Normal	Normal	normal	Overeducated	Overeducated	Overeducated
Graduat	Undereducated	Normal	normal	Overeducated	Overeducated	Overeducated
Bac	Undereducated	Undereducated	normal	Normal	Overeducated	Overeducated
PPS, D4	Undereducated	Undereducated	Undereducated	Normal	normal	Overeducated
Brevet CO	Undereducated	Undereducated	Undereducated	Undereducated	Normal	Normal
Certificate, without a diploma	Undereducated	Undereducated	Undereducated	Undereducated	Normal	Normal

Source: the creation of the author from Larcier codes on Labor Law and Social Security.

The estimation of the parameters of the multinomial logit

The parameters are estimated by maximizing the log-likelihood as a function of the vector of the parameters β . Furthermore, the log-likelihood function of a multinomial logit model being globally concave, the numerical optimization algorithms guarantee that the optimal solution is not constrained by the choice of the initial condition.

Thus, according to the model, the explained variable which is downgrading upon hiring, takes 1 if the individual is in an over-classification situation, 2 if he is in a normal state, and 3 if he is in a downgrading situation. The modeling is done thanks to the logistic function noted as follows:

The probability for an individual *i* to be downgraded is given by the following expression:

$$Pri = Prob (Y = 1) = \phi (Yi * = \beta 0 + \beta 1 SCestimé + \beta 2 SEX + \beta 3 AGE + \beta 4 DIPLOM + \beta 5 CONTRAT + \beta 6 STATMAT + \beta 7 TAILLP + \beta 8 SECTEP + \beta 9 DURRECH + \beta 10 OLD + \epsilon i$$

Where (SEX) represents the sex, (AGE) age, (STATMAT) marital status, (DIPLOM) diploma, (TAILLP) company size, (CONTRACT) the type of contract, (OLD) seniority, (DURRECH) duration of unemployment, (SECTEP) the sector of activity.

The sample used consists of 3639 employees for the year 2012 and 6469 employees for the year 2018 distributed across the country as follows:

Table 3: Distribution of the sample by province

Province	2012		2018	
	Effective	Frequency %	Effective	Frequency %
Kinshasa	854	23.48	1738	26.86
Kwango, Kwilu and Mai-ndombe	340	9.35	609	9.42
Kongo central	250	6.98	423	6.54
Lualaba, high lomani and high katanga, tanganika	679	18.66	876	13.54
Kasai orientale, Tshopo, bas uele, haut uele and ituri	225	6.17	239	3.70
Lomani, sankuru and oriental kasai	145	3.39	471	7.28
Ecuador, Mongala, Tshuapa, north Ubangi and south Ubangi	286	7.86	432	6.68
North Kivu	309	8.49	493	7.62
Maniema	69	1.91	423	6.54
South Kivu	177	4.89	157	2.43
Kasai central and kasai	304	8.36	608	9.39
Total	3638	100		1000

Source: results obtained from the base

From the table above we can note that 23% of employees in 2012 and 27% in 2018 resided in the city of Kinshasa province, followed by Katanga (18% in 2012 and 13% in 2018). Maniema in 2012 and South Kivu in 2018 are the provinces with the lowest numbers.

Table 4: analyzes of quantitative variables

Variables	2012				2018			
	Mean	Std dev	Min	Max	Mean	Std dev	Min	Max
Age	40.374	12.267	15	98	40.81	13.36	15	99
Seniority	10.688	10.51	0	56	9.975	10.041	0	52

Source: author's design based on 1-2-3 survey data

For the two years (2012 and 2018) of study, the average age of workers is 40 years with standard deviations of 12,267 and 13.36 respectively. The minimum age is 15 and the maximum is 98 for 2012 and 99 for 2018. This average around 40 is explained by the difficult integration of young people leaving the education

system into the labor market hit by a high youth unemployment rate (BCC, 2017). However, the results indicate that seniority in the labor market is on average 10 years for the two years, with standard deviations of 10.51 and 10.041 respectively for 2012 and 2018.

Table 5: descriptive analyzes of qualitative variables

Characteristics	Effective	2012		2018	
		Frequency	Frequency	Frequency	Frequency
Sex	Man	2963	81.83	4982	77.01
	Women	675	18.57	1487	22.99
Matt situation	Single	599	16.46	1151	17.80
	Married Monog	2497	68.64	4068	62.88
	Married Poly	151	4.15	316	4.89
	Free Union	165	4.54	445	6.88
	Divorced	115	3.17	226	3.95
	Widower widow	111	3.04	233	3.60
	Level of education	No			410
	Primary	456	12.55	634	9.79
	Secondary	2467	66.81	3699	57.17
	Non Formal Prog	71	1.95	35	0.53
	University	610	16.78	1551	23.28
	Post university	34	0.92	60	0.93
	Professional			80	1.24
CSP	Direct Frame	245	6.74	366	5.66
	Collab frame	530	14.57	867	13.41
	Master Agent	404	11.09	845	13.06
	Qualified work	1.308	35.97	2116	32.71
	S-Qual worker	622	17.10	1159	17.92
	Maneuver	529	14.54	1116	17.24
Type of company	Admin Pub	1510	41.51	2265.0392	35.01
	Ese Para Pub	591	16.23	1013.799	15.67
	Private Ese	1170	32.16	2510.493	38.81
	NGO	281	7.71	104.274 282	1.61 4.36
	Ese Associative	87	2.39	293.451	4.54
Total		3638	100	6469	100

Source: author's design based on 1-2-3 survey data

The results from the table above show that men constitute the majority of salaried workers in the DRC. In fact, in 2012 men represented 81% salaried workers against 19% of women. In 2018, men represented 77.08% compared to 22.89% of women. The low participation of Congolese women in the labor market seems to be explained by a division within households, between income-generating activities, which would rather be the responsibility of men, and domestic activities rather intended for women but also and above all by a level low education from women.

However, both in 2012 and in 2018, the majority of employees mainly consist of monogamous married people, i.e. 68% and 63% respectively. Singles represent 16% in 2012 and 17% in 2018. Also, we note that the level of education is low in DRC. The majority of employees hold a secondary school diploma (69% in 2012 and 57% in 2018). However, although having a higher level diploma is an asset to access strategic positions, only around 20% of Congolese workers hold a university diploma this for the years 2012 and 2018.

In all of our respondents, the executives represent 6.74% in 2012 and 5.66% in 2018, the collaboration executives are 14.67% and 13.41% respectively for the year 2012 and the year 2018. The workers are a large majority in the country, with at least 50% of salaried jobs for all two bases. General laborers saw their number increase slightly from 14% in 2012 to 18% in 2018. This large proportion of blue-collar workers can be explained by the low investment of Congolese in human capital.

The breakdown by the institutional sector of jobs is a synthetic indicator of the structure of the labor market in the DRC. Our results indicate that the public sector occupies the first place: 41.51% of workers in 2012 are employed there at the national level and 35% in 2018. The results also indicate that 32% of employees in 2012 and 36% in 2018 worked in the sector formal private sector and other sectors, including international organizations, associations, and households being poorly represented.

Knowing the profile of our respondents, it is therefore important to measure the relationship between their level of education and the job category they hold. The following section measures the level of downgrading on hiring in the DRC.

The determinants of downgrading on hiring: model estimation

This section presents the results of the econometric estimation. To do this, we model the probability of being downgraded, upgraded, or not downgraded using an independent multinomial model. The referenced variable is the fact of not being downgraded, that is to say, being in a normal situation.

Although the pseudo R2 is low 0.1696 for 2012 and 0.1711 for 2018, the Chi two and the critical probability associated with it shows that the model, as specified, is globally significant. Many variables are significant, but some have more influence than others. This is the case, for example, with diplomas. Similarly, the variables representing career paths such as seniority, age, and duration of unemployment are all significant. Other variables are only partly characteristic of downgrading.

Table 6: Estimation of the logit model

Sur-Classement	Déclassement				Sur-Classement	déclassement			
	Risk ratio	P>z	Risk ratio	P>z		Risk ratio	P>z	Risk ratio	P>z
_Cons	.06147331 (1.33)	0.182	6.92319 (-8.07)	0.000	.06147331 (1.33)	0.182	-6.923199 (-8.07)	0.000	
Sex									
Man	.7958995	2.0*	.888996	-0.81*	1.156826	-1.48**	1.025494	-0.32**	
Woman									

Age	.9986077		-0.734	.9434004	-7.53*	1.007561	2.32***	.9781458	-7.06*
Situation Matr.									
Monogamous groom	1.237924		1.60	.9711235	-0.18	.8262697	-1.51**	.578091	-6.12*
Polygamy groom	1.445106 .9776482		1.64	.6033463	-1.16	1.061035 .4727138	0.33	.685255	-2.33**
free Union	.6281922		-0.11	.7112457	-0.99	.4171273	-3.58*	.5046985	-4.75*
Divorced	.8179808		-1.65	.2187661	-2.46	.7937001	-3.43*	.6969638	-2.19**
Widowed			-0.71	.8624309	-0.28		-1.02	.9112831	-0.47
Single (ref)									
Diploma Certificate			2.48**						
CO patent	1.355482		1.24	9.63e-08	-0.04	.5243058	4.35*		-
D4, A3	1.281671 .3287134								0.12***
PP5	.4602545		-4.84*	1.19e-07	-0.02*	.2925442	-10.25*	4.25e-09	5.56*
D6, A4	.3713811		2.84**	1.720477	1.42	3.60e-09	-0.01	1.775111 .8882347	-0.29
Graduate	.2070288		-7.87*	2.334482	2.17**	.2841575	-9.18*	2.557587 1.603472	8.12*
Bachelor	3.73e-09		-8.29*	2.737215	5.17* 7.96*	2.18e-09	-0.01**	.1690791	1.40*
Doctorate				2.733052	3.30*				
None (ref)	4.69e-09		-0.02	9.885948	3.64*	.3740459	-3.37*		-3.69*
			-0.01						
						38			
Type of Ese									
Ese Para public	.4972354		-	.6370089	-	.5298582	-6.15*	.9199633	-0.90
Private Ese			5.90*		2.50***	.3731951	-9.43*	1.704341	6.79*
NGO	.4315167		-	1.247627	1.54	.7232632	-1.00	1.9881173	2.93**
Ese Associative	.94211103		7.79*	1.248946	0.95	1.453003	2.38***	1.407769	2.13***
Housework	.1156786		0.707	1.482791	0.90	.088138	-6.47*	2.046644	4.28*
Ese pub (ref)	1.034149		-	.984501	-1.48*		-	.9840159	-3.50*
Seniority	1.0983		5.56*	.9200418	-	1.048499	3.45*		
Ese size			6.74*		0.50***		-	1.448037	-3.02*
Gde ese			0.77			.5446638	2.45***		
SME (ref)									
Contract CDD			0.71		0.16	1.048499	0.33	1.129585 1.453579	1.09
Verbal agreement	1.130129 .5542073		-	1.038068 .9742711	-0.15	.605522	-3.87*		4.21*
Without contract	.8442645		4.78*	1.087162	0.52	1.10111	1.08	1.313678	3.49*
			-1.48						

CDI (ref)									
Duration of unemployment	2.733052	2.24*	1.784575	3.30*	1.01244	2.24**	2.314524	4.46*	

Source: author's conception from 1-2-3 data

Significance at the 1% threshold, ** Significance at the 5% threshold, *** Significance at the 10% threshold

LR chi2 = 1090.00 Prob> chi2 = 0.0000 Pseudo R2 = 0.1696 (for 2012) LR chi2 = 988.39 Prob> chi2 = 0.0000 Pseudo R2 = 0.17 (for 2018)

Economic interpretation and discussion

The negative and significant sign of the male modality in 2012 as in 2018 suggests that men suffer less from downgrading than women. This result is all the more coherent as women in general, take fewer risks and would venture less in the search for another job and would more readily accept a situation of guaranteed downgrading.

Men, compared to women, have a lower risk of being downgraded, at least that's what the results show.

In the Congolese context, this would be explained by the fact that the woman is less able to look for a job in places far from her family environment, thus accepting less qualified jobs near her home.

The results indicate that age has a negative influence on the probability of being downgraded. Taking age in parallel with seniority in the company, we also notice that downgrading decreases with seniority, this variable reflecting both the effect of age and the effect of generation.

As far as the effect of age is concerned, the result suggests either a gradual reclassification to jobs more in line with the diploma acquired, thanks to the experience acquired in work. Another explanation to be provided here is related to the mobility of the downgraded worker. According to matching theories, overeducated individuals should be more mobile on average

As for the diploma variable, it is significant, both on the probability of being upgraded and on the probability of being downgraded compared to the probability of being effectively downgraded. About downgrading, the results indicate that the diploma acts positively on downgrading.

In 2012 as in 2018, compared to individuals without a diploma, the results indicate that having a certificate or a C.O. certificate has a negative influence on the probability of being downgraded. In addition, all other things being equal, the other levels of the diploma positively influence downgrading. It is obvious that individuals with a high diploma are therefore more likely to find themselves downgraded.

Furthermore, the diploma significantly and negatively influences the probability of being upgraded. Indeed, having a high diploma reduces the risk of being upgraded and in the same way, having a low level of diploma increases the probability of being upgraded. The results obtained show that compared to individuals without any qualification, having a primary school certificate and a CO certificate positively influences the probability of being outperformed in 2012, on the other hand in 2018, all levels of qualification negatively influence the probability of d 'be upgraded.

The nature of the business has an influence on the likelihood of downgrading but also of over-ranking. The results indicate that all other things being equal, in 2012 as in 2018, employment in the private sector negatively influences the probability of being upgraded. In addition, compared to the public sector, all other business sectors positively influence the probability of being downgraded in 2018.

For the duration of the unemployment variable, it appears in the estimate with a positive sign; its impact on decommissioning is solid and significant. Indeed, there is every reason to believe that, according to the theory of queuing discussed above, the longer the wait for a first job, the higher the propensity to accept a downgraded job. However, [Giret 2003], after two comparative surveys on the measure of downgrading, maintains that five years after leaving the education system, young unemployed graduates are forced to accept less qualified jobs when they first work.

However, for firm size, it is important to note that this variable has a negative and significant influence on the probability of being downgraded. This result suggests that the larger a company, the less human capital is underutilized.

GENERAL CONCLUSION

The results of the application of the statistical method indicate the degrees of downgrading of 10.01 and 29.83% respectively for the years 2012 and 2018 with an over-classification rate of 28.08 and 16.54%. As illustrated in the literature, downgrading affects the most educated individuals, ie an over-education rate of 25% on average for tertiary graduates, 20% for secondary school graduates, and less than 15% for other diploma levels. The results of the econometric estimate indicate that downgrading is a positive function of the level of the diploma and decreases with seniority in the company. Also, other factors explain the downgrade, namely: gender, industry, age, length of time unemployed, promotion, and type of contract.

Given the downgrading, it is not only necessary but above all urgent to question the possibilities of correcting these discrepancies between the supply and demand for skills. The economic perspective suggests that the good functioning of the system is associated with low levels of mismatch between skills produced and skills required by jobs.

Thus, financial regulation and quantitative regulation of the workforce in the education system via the training-employment relationship are tools for controlling the supply of training related to the external efficiency of the education system. As a result, the following elements are necessary today in the DRC: financial regulation of school flows, quantitative regulation of school and university flows through the training-employment relationship, regulation through information and vocational guidance, and regulation by the quality of education.

This research places its originality in the fact that it is the first to tackle, in the context of the DRC, the question linked to downgrading on hiring. It thus constructs a correspondence table which crosses diplomas and socio-professional categories and which, for employment policy purposes, could serve as an orientation tool.

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